

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP7 – Information and data governance, ethics, technology and data catalogue and quality support

D7.18 Report confirming all relevant documents for using, producing or collecting human cells or tissues (e.g. ethics approval, import licence, accreditation/designation/authorisation /licensing) prior to start of research raising ethical issues are on file

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Document history

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Table of Contents

Document history	1
Abstract.....	3
Abbreviations	3
<i>Purpose and scope of this document</i>	3
Background	4
Work Package 3	4
Work Package 4	4
Task description	4
Table 1. Ethical documentation for WP3.....	6
Table 2. Ethical documentation for WP4.....	7
Availability	8
Conclusion.....	9
References.....	9

Abstract

Started in 2019, the ConcePTION project aims to establish a large ecosystem to provide fast and reliable evidence on drug safety during pregnancy and breastfeeding. ConcePTION partners are conducting studies across Europe, some of them with the close collaboration of pregnant and breastfeeding women, which is one of the cornerstones of the project.

As described in the research proposal, certain tasks in work packages involve the collection of human cells or tissues. In this report on deliverable D7.18, we describe the collection and public availability of the ethical documentation for work package 3 and 4.

Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of Action
IRB	Institutional Review Board
HCP	Health Care Providers
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DP	Demonstration Project
SOP	Standard Operational Procedures

Purpose and scope of this document

One of the purposes of WP7 in the ConcePTION project is to provide ethical, governance, and quality assessment support for the conduct of distributed data collection and analyses which support the generation of high-quality real-world evidence. Task 7.10 involves collecting copies from all templates, Institutional Review Board (IRB) comments and approvals, and documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical and IMI obligations.

The purpose of deliverable D7.18 is to describe the collection of ethical documentation of the activities carry out within work package 3 and 4 that involves the prospective collection of human tissue or cells within the ConcePTION project, with the aim to made available how studies comply with current ethical and local governance requirements.

From the ConcePTION Description of Action (DoA), D7.18 description is:

“Report confirming that all the relevant documents for using, producing, or collecting human cells or tissues (e.g., ethics approval, import license, accreditation, designation, authorization, licensing) prior to the start of the research activity raising ethics issue and that they are kept on file”

Background

ConcePTION aims to create an ecosystem for the rapid and robust generation of evidence on the safety of medications in pregnancy and lactation, using both existing and newly generated real-world data. The present report is one of the five deliverables in task 7.10 and involves our partners from WP3 and WP4.

Task 7.10 of WP7 is described as follows in the ConcePTION Description of Action (DoA):

“In this task we will collect copies from all templates, IRB review comments and approvals and documentation from the sites that are required to comply with the ethical (see section 5) and IMI obligations. This task will deliverable five deliverables (D7.18-7.22), providing proof and documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant.”

Work Package 3

The main objective of WP3 is to develop, characterise, validate, and apply a non-clinical testing platform for reliable prediction of drug concentrations in human breast milk along with systemic drug exposure in breastfed infants.

Briefly, task 3.2 in WP3 consist of developing an improved *in vitro* model for drug passage from maternal blood to human breast milk using cultured human mammary epithelial cells. At least 10 model compounds selected will be used in the first wave of *in vitro* experiments.

Work Package 4

The main objective of WP4 is to establish a central European self-sustaining breast milk and blood biobank and analytical centres able to comply with regulatory quality standards fit for label, capable of measuring medication concentrations in breast milk. The same drugs are used in WP3 for the development and validation of non-clinical models. Prospective samples were collected from clinical care through pregnancy exposure registries and research through partners' networks across the consortium in collaboration with WP2 and 5.

Documentation in relation to demonstration projects (task 4.3) measuring medications in breast milk and maternal blood/plasma is provided in D7.21. In the present report, we considered only the documentation related to the establishment of the breastmilk biobank, that is task 4.1 and 4.2. WP4 has developed information and consent procedures for recruitment of potential participants in collection of breast milk samples for storage in a European Biobank (4.1) and subsequently being used for pharmacokinetic analyses of if, and to what extent, medical drugs transfer from breast milk to the breast-feeding child (4.2). In addition, procedures for collecting breast milk and blood have been developed to facilitate research collecting blood and breast milk.

Task description

This deliverable report is based on the collection of ethical documentation, that is – templates, informed consent procedures, informed consent sheets, participant's information sheets, Standard Operational Procedures (SOP), Data Management Plan (DMP), and Data Impact Protection Assessment (DPIA), if applicable. The aim is to provide proof and public documentation that ConcePTION partners and third parties are compliant with their ethical and local governance requirements.

The scope of this deliverable is ethical and governance documentation related to studies in which prospective primary data collection involving samples of breastmilk is performed. It is not part of this deliverable to monitor or audit whether information provision, consent procedures, or ethical approvals were conducted according to national/regional guidelines or local requirements where the studies will take place or whether they followed the recommendation from the ConcePTION consortium ([Singleton & Cunnington 2020](#)).

From September 2022 to September 2023, we approached WP and DP leads via e-mail requesting the aforementioned documentation. [Table 1](#) and [Table 2](#) show the **studies**, the **documentation** shared, the **name of the files** in the IMI-ConcePTION Member area, and the **contact person** who handled the documentation till the moment of the submission of the present report. We expect partners to still contribute to this 'live' report with further documentation once they receive approvals by uploading files in the corresponding repository.

Table 1. Ethical documentation for WP3

STUDY	DOCUMENTATION SHARED WITH WP7	NAME OF THE FILE IN IMI-CONCEPTION MEMBER AREA	CONTACT PERSON IN WP3
Task 3.2	✓ SOP	3e-Tissue Compliance_October 2019[4].pdf 3f-A10565 2098293[2].pdf SCC139(5).pdf	Anthony de Lise anthony.delise[at]novartis[dot]com
	✓ Product information sheet	CRL-10317.pdf HTB-22(3).pdf MAN0001573_HMEC_Pi.pdf	
	✓ Safety data sheet	msds_animal.pdf	
	✓ REACH registration number	9Q03DQ_Sub_SDS_BE_FR.PDF	
Contact WP lead for further information. ✓ Available in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area			

Table 2. Ethical documentation for WP4

STUDY	DOCUMENTATION SHARED WITH WP7	NAME OF THE FILE IN IMI-CONCEPTION MEMBER AREA	CONTACT PERSON IN WP4
Task 4.1	✓ DMP	IMI2_Deliverable ConcePTION, 4.3.pdf	Charlotte Daire Charlotte.Daire[at]chuv[dot]ch
	✓ Protocol template	IMI2_Deliverable ConcePTION, 4.3.pdf	
	✓ Sample protocol	IMI2_Deliverable ConcePTION, 4.3.pdf	
		11. Instructions_échantillonnage_Venlafaxine_20211222.pdf 11. Fiche_échantillonnage_Venlafaxine_20211222.pdf	
	✓ Information sheet	IMI2_Deliverable ConcePTION, 4.3.pdf	
	✓ Consent form	IMI2_Deliverable ConcePTION, 4.3.pdf	
	✓ SOP	8. Description_of_operation_uppsala_biobank_20210330.pdf	
Task 4.2	<input type="radio"/> DMP <input type="radio"/> Protocol <input type="radio"/> IRB approval		Charlotte Daire Charlotte.Daire[at]chuv[dot]ch

○ Not available. Contact WP lead further information.

✓ Available in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area

Availability

We proposed to make the documentation available via the [IMI-ConcePTION Member Area](#) to allow related WP leads/members to upload their documentation after the date of submission of this deliverable, if deemed necessary. Each WP has been assigned a folder in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area where they can store related documentation (Figure 1). In the case of WP4, they will need to create a folder named 'Ethics deliveries' where to store the related documentation.

The present report will be made available as 'Files' in the public repository ([Zenodo – IMI ConcePTION](#)), after approval of this report. The report will be in the public domain, and available for download.

Figure 1. Example of repository for related documentation in the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area

Documents

The screenshot displays a file management interface for 'Work package 3 > 2- Ethics Deliverables > In vivo studies'. The left sidebar shows a hierarchical folder structure including '0- WP3 Management Meeting', '1- WP3 Meetings', '2- Ethics Deliverables', 'D3.6 Generic PBPK', 'In vitro - Cell Cultures', 'In vivo studies', and various tasks under 'Task 3'. The main area shows a list of three PDF files:

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name	Date modified	Size
<input type="checkbox"/>	3b- AutRigMinistero[1181]Approvazione_Notifica_BDN_Forni_1181.pdf	11/10/2022 3:35 PM	454.2 KB
<input type="checkbox"/>	3c- AutRigMinistero [1185]Autorizzazione_202132_Bacci_1185.pdf new.pdf	11/10/2022 3:57 PM	162.7 KB
<input type="checkbox"/>	AutRigMinistero[1282]Autorizzazione_202335_Bacci_1282.pdf	8/11/2023 5:05 PM	789.0 KB

At the bottom, it shows 'Items per Page: 10' and '3 Items'.

Conclusion

The present Report provides an overview of the ethical documentation related to the use of human mammary epithelial cells in WP3 and the collection of human breastmilk samples in WP4. Before the submission of this deliverable, participating members provided the information and/or documentation stated in this report through the IMI-ConcePTION Member Area. We expect further ethical documentation to be made available through the same media after the approval of this deliverable.

References

Singleton, P., & Cunnington, M. (2020). Report on initial information and research governance for WP1-5 (D7.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5840292>